

THE ROLE OF ELECTRONIC WORD OF MOUTH IN MEDIATING THE EFFECT OF SOCIAL MEDIA MARKETING ON PURCHASE INTENTION (A Study on Prospective Skintific Consumers in Denpasar City)

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Abstract

The rapid development of digital technology has encouraged companies to utilize social media as a strategic marketing tool. This study aims to examine the role of electronic word of mouth in mediating the effect of social media marketing on purchase intention among prospective Skintific consumers in Denpasar City. This study employs the stimulus–organism–response (S-O-R) theory as its theoretical foundation, where social media marketing acts as the stimulus, electronic word of mouth as the organism, and purchase intention as the response. This research is associative in nature with a quantitative approach. Data were collected through an online questionnaire using Google Forms distributed to 130 respondents selected through purposive sampling. Data analysis was conducted using descriptive and inferential statistics with SEM-PLS through SmartPLS 4.0. The results indicate that social media marketing has a positive and significant effect on purchase intention and electronic word of mouth. Furthermore, electronic word of mouth also has a positive and significant effect on purchase intention and partially mediates the relationship between social media marketing and purchase intention. These findings suggest that social media marketing strategies not only directly increase purchase intention but also indirectly through electronic word of mouth, which strengthens trust and positive perceptions of prospective consumers toward Skintific products.

Keywords: social media marketing, electronic word of mouth, purchase intention

INTRODUCTION

The rapid advancement of digital technology has brought significant changes to global business and marketing practices. Digital transformation has not only altered companies' operational systems and communication strategies but has also influenced how companies understand and build long-term relationships with consumers. According to a survey released by the Indonesian Internet Service Providers Association (APJII) in 2025, the internet penetration rate in Indonesia reached 80.66%, equivalent to approximately 229.4 million people out of a total population of 284.4 million. This figure represents an increase of 1.6% compared to the previous period in 2024, when internet penetration was recorded at 79.50%. This increase indicates that digital connectivity has become an integral part of Indonesian society, reflecting a major shift toward a more digitally integrated community (Fikri & Junaidi, 2024).

The growth of social media usage has also transformed companies' marketing strategies in building brand image and attracting consumer purchase intention. Social

media platforms such as Instagram, TikTok, YouTube, Facebook, and Twitter now serve as strategic platforms for companies to interact with consumers (Salarno, 2025). Through engaging visual content, collaborations with influencers, and interactive campaigns, companies seek to create emotional connections with their audience (Khaira et al., 2025). This trend has led to the emergence of social media marketing as a communication strategy that focuses not only on product promotion but also on building digital communities that encourage active consumer engagement (Maslahatun et al., 2025).

Changes in marketing strategies are particularly evident in industries that rely heavily on visual appeal and consumer experience, such as the beauty and skincare industry. In this sector, social media functions not only as a promotional channel but also as a medium to build emotional connections between brands and consumers. Through engaging visual messages, authentic testimonials, and shared user experiences, companies can foster closeness and trust in their products (Budiarti, 2025). Modern consumers are no longer passive recipients of advertising messages; instead, they actively seek information, watch product reviews, and compare other users' experiences before making purchasing decisions (Zed et al., 2025).

Skintific once ranked first in the beauty bundle category on Shopee Indonesia in the first quarter of 2025, with a market share of approximately 7%, followed by MS Glow at 6.9% and Glad2Glow at 4.9% (Compas.co.id, 2025). These findings also indicate that bundled products are increasingly popular due to their practicality and added value for consumers. However, based on updated data from Compas.co.id in the second quarter of 2025, Skintific's position declined to second place, overtaken by MS Glow, which increased its market share to 7.26%, while Skintific recorded 6.49%. Despite receiving many positive reviews and being supported by intensive social media marketing strategies, some consumers have also expressed negative reviews regarding their product experiences. Negative reviews on e-commerce platforms highlight complaints such as skin peeling, results not matching claims, uncomfortable product texture, and incorrect or incomplete product delivery. These reviews are documented in Appendix 8. This variation in experiences indicates that consumer perceptions of Skintific are not entirely homogeneous, even when the company strives to maintain consistent marketing messages through social media.

The decline in market share in the beauty bundle segment has occurred despite Skintific's continued active implementation of social media marketing strategies, such as promotional content and influencer collaborations. This dynamic suggests that marketing messages delivered through social media do not always align with actual consumer experiences and perceptions (Efendioğlu & Durmaz, 2022). It also indicates that the effectiveness of social media marketing depends not only on the intensity of activities but also on content attractiveness, strategy relevance, and the brand's ability to adapt to changing consumer trends and preferences (Voorveld et al., 2018). In a highly competitive digital market, social media marketing is not merely a promotional tool but a strategic factor that determines the extent to which consumer purchase intention can be influenced while maintaining brand competitiveness (Felix et al., 2020).

At the regional level, particularly in Denpasar City, similar trends have been observed. Based on offline observations conducted in December 2025 at several

cosmetic stores and beauty outlets in Denpasar, including Watson and Guardian at Level 21 Mall and Sociolla at Living World Denpasar, a significant shift in skincare product sales patterns was identified. These outlets were selected due to their high consumer traffic and representation of the beauty market in Denpasar.

The findings reveal that Skintific products, which previously dominated prime display areas, have gradually been replaced by other brands. Interviews with sales promotion staff indicated a declining sales trend in recent months, particularly in the full skincare series category. Consumers are becoming more cautious, often seeking reviews before purchasing and sometimes canceling their purchase intentions after encountering negative feedback regarding product effectiveness.

This decline is further reflected in changes in product display strategies, where Skintific products are now placed in less strategic positions. This phenomenon highlights a shift in consumer preferences in Denpasar, influenced not only by digital promotion intensity but also by user experiences shared through online reviews. These findings reinforce that Skintific's social media marketing strategies have not been fully effective in maintaining consumer purchase intention in Denpasar.

This phenomenon highlights the importance of understanding consumer behavior, particularly purchase intention, which forms the basis of actual purchasing decisions. Philip Kotler and Kevin Lane Keller (2016:198) define purchase intention as a consumer's tendency or willingness to buy a particular product in the future based on evaluation, experience, and brand preferences. Purchase intention is also considered an important indicator of actual buying behavior as it reflects the psychological stage prior to the purchase decision (Zahratu & Hurriyati, 2020). The formation of purchase intention is influenced by various factors, such as consumer needs and perceptions of a product (Faresha, 2020). Additionally, purchase intention may arise when consumers receive appealing information about a product through advertisements, user reviews, or recommendations from others (Soefhwan & Kurniawati, 2022). The increasingly massive flow of information in the digital environment has positioned social media as a primary channel for consumers to obtain information, making social media marketing an essential factor in shaping purchase intention.

Mileva and Fauzi (2018) define social media marketing as the process of promoting products or services through social platforms by leveraging broad digital communities. With technological advancements, social media is no longer used solely for information sharing but has become a strategic space for companies to interact directly with consumers. Interactive features and the presence of influencers make marketing messages more engaging and easily accepted by audiences (Redjeki, 2025). Social media marketing also enables companies to reach audiences in real time and obtain rapid feedback, thereby strengthening relationships with consumers (Velooso et al., 2023). This approach allows companies to deliver value more responsively to customers (Nuseir et al., 2023), while also creating more dynamic interactions through direct communication (Purnomo, 2023). Furthermore, social media offers more cost-efficient promotional opportunities and helps enhance brand visibility in a competitive digital environment (Ahmed et al., 2025).

The rapid advancement of technology has encouraged companies to optimize social media as part of their marketing efforts. Through social media marketing,

companies are expected to attract consumer attention and influence the emergence of purchase intention. Research by Aprilianti et al. (2023) shows that social media marketing has a positive effect on purchase intention. Similar findings were reported by Sutariningsih and Widagda (2021), who found a positive and significant influence of social media marketing on purchase intention. However, not all studies yield consistent results. Diventy et al. (2020) found that social media marketing does not have a significant effect on purchase intention.

Based on this research gap, a mediating variable is needed to bridge the relationship between social media marketing and purchase intention, namely electronic word of mouth (E-WOM). E-WOM refers to the dissemination of information, opinions, and consumer experiences through digital media, enabling messages to spread rapidly and widely. The ease of internet access has shaped consumer behavior, making them increasingly accustomed to seeking comments or reviews before making a purchase, while the information obtained from such reviews plays a role in enhancing consumer trust in the product (Noviandini & Yasa, 2021). E-WOM also represents an informal form of communication that influences purchasing decisions in both the short and long term (Wijaya et al., 2022).

Skintific utilizes user reviews and experiences as social proof to reinforce its marketing messages, thereby increasing consumer trust and reducing uncertainty (Penny & Makaba, 2024). Research by Hardono (2024) indicates that social media marketing has a significant effect on E-WOM. In contrast, Azizah and Hartanti (2017) found that social media marketing does not have a significant effect on E-WOM.

Consumer purchasing decisions today are strongly influenced by recommendations and social trust, where customer reviews or electronic word of mouth serve as primary sources of information prior to the formation of purchase intention. This is consistent with research by Fitri and Isa (2024), which shows that E-WOM has a positive and significant effect on purchase intention. Similar results were found by Fontaine et al. (2025), where E-WOM was proven to drive consumer purchase intention. The consistent positive relationship between E-WOM and purchase intention makes E-WOM a relevant mediating variable in this study. Moreover, Prasad et al. (2017) argue that social media promotion will have a stronger impact when supported by positive reviews, as it enhances perceived value and consumer interest in the product.

Based on this background, this study aims to examine the role of electronic word of mouth in mediating the effect of social media marketing on purchase intention for Skintific products in Denpasar City. This study adopts the stimulus–organism–response (S-O-R) theory to explain the process of purchase intention formation. The S-O-R theory, introduced by Albert Mehrabian and James A. Russell (1974), states that external stimuli (S) received by individuals influence their internal state or organism (O), which subsequently leads to a behavioral response (R). In this study, social media marketing is positioned as the stimulus, electronic word of mouth as the organism representing internal evaluation processes, and purchase intention as the resulting response.

RESEARCH METHOD

This study employs a causal associative research design to analyze the relationships and effects among variables, namely the influence of social media

marketing on purchase intention, both directly and indirectly through electronic word of mouth as a mediating variable. This approach aims to explain cause-and-effect relationships between variables using questionnaires as the primary data collection instrument. The research location was set in Denpasar City due to its characteristics as an economic center with a high level of internet penetration, making it relevant for examining digital consumer behavior, particularly for Skintific beauty products (Sugiyono, 2023; Krismajayanti et al., 2025; Antari et al., 2025).

The object of this study focuses on consumer behavior reflected in purchase intention, with social media marketing as the independent variable and electronic word of mouth as the mediating variable. The study population consists of prospective consumers who have never purchased Skintific products in Denpasar, with a sample size of 130 respondents determined using a non-probability sampling technique with a purposive sampling approach. The data used include both qualitative and quantitative data derived from primary sources (questionnaires) and secondary sources (relevant literature). Data collection was conducted online using Google Forms, employing a Likert scale to measure respondents' perceptions of the variables studied (Sugiyono, 2023).

Data analysis was carried out using descriptive and inferential statistical approaches with the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) method based on Partial Least Squares (PLS) using SmartPLS 4. Model evaluation includes the outer model to test the validity and reliability of the instruments, and the inner model to examine the relationships between variables through R^2 values, t-statistics, and p-values. In addition, mediation testing was conducted to determine the role of electronic word of mouth in the relationship between social media marketing and purchase intention. The results indicate that all indicators are valid and reliable, thus the model is appropriate for hypothesis testing and drawing research conclusions (Hair et al., 2022; Ghozali & Latan, 2015).

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Company Overview

Skintific is a skincare brand originating from Canada, with its name derived from a combination of the words skin and scientific. The brand was developed by Kristen Tveit and Ann-Kristin Stokke, and was first introduced in 1957 in Oslo, Norway (Skintific.id, 2026). The main vision of Skintific is to create high-quality skincare products accessible to a wide range of consumers through intelligent formulations based on Trilogy Triangle Effect (TTE) technology, which is claimed to be safe for sensitive skin and supports long-term skin barrier health (Tempo.co, 2023).

Skintific officially entered the Indonesian market in August 2021 by offering various skincare products, such as moisturizers, face masks, toners, cleansers, and serums. One of its most popular products in Indonesia is the 5X Ceramide Barrier Repair Moisture Gel. Currently, Skintific's production process is carried out through an Original Design Manufacturer (ODM), namely Guangdong Essence Daily Chemical Co., Ltd. in China, while distribution and official licensing in Indonesia are managed by PT May Sun Yvan (IDN Times, 2024). In addition to product development, Skintific actively builds its digital presence through Instagram and TikTok. As of 2026, Skintific has approximately

1 million followers on Instagram and 3.7 million followers on TikTok, indicating strong brand exposure and consumer engagement.

Respondent Characteristics

Table 1. Respondent Characteristics

No	Characteristics	Classification	Number of Respondents (persons)	Percentage (%)
1	Gender	Female	98	75.4
		Male	32	24.6
		Total	130	100
2	Age	18–21 years	54	41.5
		22–25 years	51	39.2
		26–30 years	20	15.4
		>30 years	5	3.9
		Total	130	100
3	Education	Senior High School/Vocational School	71	54.6
		Diploma (D1/D2/D3)	16	12.4
		Bachelor’s Degree (S1)	41	31.5
		Others	2	1.5
		Total	130	100
4	Occupation	Students	65	50
		Civil Servants	8	6.2
		Private Employees	33	25.3
		Entrepreneurs	20	15.4
		Others	4	3.1
		Total	130	100

Source: Processed data, 2026.

The majority of respondents are female (75.4%), indicating that prospective consumers of Skintific products in Denpasar City are predominantly women who are more actively engaged in skincare and more exposed to social media marketing and electronic word of mouth, although male participation has begun to increase. In terms of age, respondents are dominated by the 18–25 age group (80.7%), which represents active social media users who are more frequently exposed to digital content.

Based on educational background, most respondents have a senior high school/vocational school education (54.6%), followed by those with a bachelor’s degree, suggesting that interest in the product is relatively widespread but stronger among individuals with a moderate level of education who actively access digital information. From an occupational perspective, respondents are primarily students (50%), who tend to have high intensity in social media usage, making them more susceptible to online reviews and recommendations in shaping their purchase intention.

Description of Research Variables

Table 2. Criteria for Variable Description

Average Score	Social Media Marketing	Electronic Word of Mouth	Purchase Intention
1.00 – 1.80	Very Poor	Very Poor	Very Low
1.81 – 2.60	Poor	Poor	Low
2.61 – 3.40	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate
3.41 – 4.20	Good	Good	High
4.21 – 5.00	Very Good	Very Good	Very High

Source: Sugiyono (2023:145)

Based on the analysis results, the purchase intention variable falls into the high category with an average score of 3.58, where interest in the product is the highest indicator, while the tendency to compare with other products is relatively lower. This indicates that purchasing decisions are more driven by attraction rather than alternative evaluation. The social media marketing variable is categorized as good with an average score of 3.64, reflected in the high attractiveness of content, although two-way interaction with the audience remains suboptimal. Furthermore, the electronic word of mouth variable is also categorized as good with an average score of 3.82, with user reviews being the most dominant factor in shaping consumer perceptions, although emotional attachment to the brand is still relatively limited. Overall, these findings confirm that consumer interest in Skintific products is supported by effective social media content and the strong influence of online reviews, although aspects of interaction and emotional engagement still need improvement.

Outer Model (Measurement Model)

1) Convergent Validity

Table 3. Convergent Validity Test Results Using Loading Factor

Variable	Indicator	Outer Loading	Description
Purchase Intention (Y)	Y1	0.770	Valid
	Y2	0.757	Valid
	Y3	0.785	Valid
	Y4	0.757	Valid
	Y5	0.836	Valid
Social Media Marketing (X)	X1	0.787	Valid
	X2	0.836	Valid
	X3	0.826	Valid
	X4	0.786	Valid
Electronic Word of Mouth (M)	M1	0.854	Valid
	M2	0.781	Valid
	M3	0.750	Valid
	M4	0.795	Valid

Source: Processed data, 2026

Table 3 shows that all outer loading values exceed 0.70, indicating that the research instruments are valid. This is further supported by the average variance extracted (AVE) values for each latent variable, which are above 0.50, meeting the criteria for convergent validity (Hair et al., 2022:119). Thus, the constructs of purchase

intention, social media marketing, and electronic word of mouth have fulfilled convergent validity, and the measurement model is considered valid and suitable for further discriminant validity testing as presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Average Variance Extracted (AVE) Results

Variable	AVE
Purchase Intention (Y)	0.642
Social Media Marketing (X)	0.684
Electronic Word of Mouth (M)	0.671

Source: Processed data, 2026

2) Discriminant validity

Table 5. Discriminant Validity Test Results (Cross Loading)

	Electronic Word of Mouth (M)	Social Media Marketing (X)	Purchase Intention (Y)
M1	0,854	0,549	0,618
M2	0,781	0,433	0,481
M3	0,750	0,541	0,551
M4	0,795	0,552	0,593
X1	0,546	0,787	0,467
X2	0,572	0,836	0,527
X3	0,535	0,826	0,532
X4	0,470	0,786	0,531
Y1	0,703	0,538	0,770
Y2	0,482	0,522	0,757
Y3	0,437	0,490	0,785
Y4	0,546	0,341	0,757
Y5	0,555	0,565	0,836

Source: Processed data, 2026

The data presented in Table 5 indicate good discriminant validity. This is shown by cross loading values exceeding 0.70 and by the fact that each indicator has a higher correlation with its respective construct than with other constructs. Additionally, discriminant validity was also tested using the Fornell–Larcker approach by examining the square root of the average variance extracted (AVE), also known as root AVE. This method compares the square root of AVE for each construct with the correlations between constructs in the model. A construct is considered to meet discriminant validity if the square root of its AVE is greater than its correlation with other constructs. The bold values in the table indicate that this criterion has been satisfied. The results of the Fornell–Larcker test are presented in Table 6.

Table 6. Fornell–Larcker Validity Test Results

	Electronic Word of Mouth (M)	Social Media Marketing (X)	Purchase Intention (Y)
Electronic Word of Mouth (M)	0,796		
Social Media Marketing (X)	0,657	0,809	
Purchase Intention (Y)	0,710	0,635	0,782

Source: Processed data, 2026

The Fornell–Larcker criterion states that the square root of AVE for each variable must be greater than the correlations between variables in the model. Based on Table 6, all variables show AVE root values higher than their correlations with other variables. The AVE root values are 0.796 for electronic word of mouth, 0.809 for social media marketing, and 0.782 for purchase intention. These results indicate that all constructs meet the discriminant validity criteria using the Fornell–Larcker approach.

Furthermore, discriminant validity was also assessed using the heterotrait–monotrait ratio (HTMT). The recommended HTMT value is below 0.90. This method is considered more sensitive and accurate in detecting discriminant validity compared to conventional methods (Hair et al., 2022:145). The HTMT test results are presented in Table 7.

Table 7. HTMT Validity Test Results

	Electronic Word of Mouth (M)	Social Media Marketing (X)	Purchase Intention (Y)
Electronic Word of Mouth (M)			
Social Media Marketing (X)	0,798		
Purchase Intention (Y)	0,838	0,753	

Source: Processed data, 2026

Based on Table 7, all HTMT values are below 0.90 for each variable pair, indicating that the correlations between different constructs are within acceptable limits. Therefore, it can be concluded that discriminant validity has been achieved.

3) Composite reliability

Table 8. Composite Reliability Test Results

Variabel Penelitian	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Keterangan
Purchase Intention (Y)	0,842	0,887	Reliabel
Social Media Marketing (X)	0,824	0,883	Reliabel
Electronic Word of Mouth (M)	0,807	0,873	Reliabel

Source: Processed data, 2026

The results in Table 8 show that all variables have Cronbach's alpha values above 0.60 and composite reliability values above 0.70. This indicates that all constructs in this study meet the reliability criteria, meaning that each variable is considered reliable or internally consistent.

Inner Model (Structural Model)

1) Inner VIF Multicollinearity Test

Table 9. Inner VIF Multicollinearity Test Results

	Purchase Intention (Y)	Electronic Word of Mouth (M)
Social Media Marketing (X)	1,758	1,000
Electronic Word of Mouth (M)	1,758	

Source: Processed data, 2026

Based on Table 9, all inner VIF values are below 5, indicating a low level of multicollinearity among variables. These results suggest that the SEM-PLS parameter estimates are robust and unbiased.

2) Nilai R-square

Table 10. Coefficient of Determination (R-square)

Research Variable	R-square	Adjusted R-square
Purchase Intention (Y)	0,554	0,547
Electronic Word of Mouth (M)	0,431	0,427

Source: Processed data, 2026

The data in Table 10 show that the R-square value for purchase intention (Y) is 0.554, which falls into the moderate category. This indicates that 55.4% of the variance in purchase intention can be explained by social media marketing (X) and electronic word of mouth (M), while the remaining 44.6% is influenced by other variables outside this research model. Furthermore, the R-square value for electronic word of mouth (M) is 0.431, also categorized as moderate, meaning that 43.1% of its variance is explained by social media marketing (X), while the remaining 56.9% is influenced by other factors not included in this study.

3) F-Square Value

Table 11. F-Square Test Results

	F-Square
Social Media Marketing → Purchase Intention	0,113
Social Media Marketing → Electronic Word of Mouth	0,758
Electronic Word of Mouth → Purchase Intention	0,338

Source: Processed data, 2026

Based on Table 11, the direct effect of social media marketing on purchase intention (0.113) falls within the small effect size category. Meanwhile, the effect of social media marketing on electronic word of mouth (0.758) exceeds 0.35, indicating a large effect size, meaning that social media marketing has a very strong contribution in explaining variations in electronic word of mouth. Additionally, the effect of electronic word of mouth on purchase intention (0.338), which is close to 0.35, indicates a strong contribution to increasing purchase intention.

4) Q-Square Value

Table 12. Q-Square Test Results

	Q ² (=1-SSE/SSO)
Purchase Intention (Y)	0,412
Electronic Word of Mouth (M)	0,388

Source: Processed data, 2026

The results in Table 12 indicate that the Q-square values for purchase intention (0.412) and electronic word of mouth (0.388) are both greater than zero. This suggests that the model has predictive relevance.

Hypothesis Testing

1) Direct Effects Test Results

Table 13. Direct Effects Test Results

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T-statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
Social media marketing (X) → Purchase intention (Y)	0,297	0,304	0,087	3,430	0,001
Social media marketing (X) → Electronic word of mouth (M)	0,657	0,662	0,070	9,380	0,000
Electronic word of mouth (M) → Purchase intention (Y)	0,515	0,510	0,088	5,869	0,000

Source: Processed data, 2026

Based on Table 13, the direct effects among variables can be explained as follows:

1) Hypothesis 1 (Effect of Social Media Marketing on Purchase Intention):

The results show that the t-statistic value (3.430) is greater than 1.96 and the p-value (0.001) is less than 0.05. This indicates that social media marketing has a significant effect on purchase intention. The path coefficient of 0.297 shows a positive relationship. Therefore, H_1 is accepted, indicating that social media marketing has a positive and significant effect on purchase intention.

2) Hypothesis 2 (Effect of Social Media Marketing on Electronic Word of Mouth):

The t-statistic value (9.380) exceeds 1.96 and the p-value (0.000) is below 0.05, indicating a significant effect. The path coefficient of 0.657 indicates a positive relationship. Thus, H_2 is accepted, confirming that social media marketing has a positive and significant effect on electronic word of mouth.

3) Hypothesis 3 (Effect of Electronic Word of Mouth on Purchase Intention):

The t-statistic value (5.869) is greater than 1.96 and the p-value (0.000) is below 0.05, indicating a significant effect. The path coefficient of 0.515 shows a positive relationship. Therefore, H_3 is accepted, meaning that electronic word of mouth has a positive and significant effect on purchase intention.

2) Indirect Effects Test Results

Table 14. Indirect Effects Test Results

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T-statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
Social media marketing (X) → Electronic word	0,338	0,335	0,058	5,838	0,000

of mouth (M) →
Purchase intention
(Y)

Source: Processed data, 2026

The results of Hypothesis 4 show that the t-statistic value (5.838) is greater than 1.96 and the p-value (0.000) is less than 0.05. The indirect path coefficient of 0.338 indicates a positive relationship between social media marketing and purchase intention through electronic word of mouth. This suggests that electronic word of mouth is able to mediate the effect of social media marketing on purchase intention. Therefore, H_4 is accepted.

Mediation Effect Testing

The mediation type was tested based on the significance of direct effects between variables following the approach of Hair et al. (2022:234). The results show that social media marketing significantly affects electronic word of mouth (p_1), electronic word of mouth significantly affects purchase intention (p_2), and social media marketing also has a significant direct effect on purchase intention (p_3), all with p-values < 0.05 . These findings indicate that all three paths (p_1 , p_2 , and p_3) are positive and significant. Since the direct effect remains significant after including the mediating variable, electronic word of mouth is classified as a partial mediation variable in this relationship.

Discussion

The results of this study indicate that social media marketing has a positive and significant effect on purchase intention, as reflected in respondents' high evaluations of the entertainment aspect of Skintific's content. This finding suggests that content attractiveness not only serves as a communication tool but also creates emotional experiences that stimulate consumer interest. From the perspective of the Stimulus-Organism-Response model, social media marketing acts as an external stimulus that triggers internal processes in the form of interest and cognitive evaluation, ultimately resulting in a behavioral response in the form of purchase intention (Harliani et al., 2025; Rahmawati & Setyowibowo, 2025). Therefore, the effectiveness of informative and entertaining content becomes a key factor in strengthening purchase intention, in line with previous studies which state that social media marketing can shape positive consumer perceptions (Pujangga et al., 2023; Sambodo, 2025).

Furthermore, the significant influence of social media marketing on electronic word of mouth indicates that engaging content encourages consumers to actively participate in sharing information and experiences online. The influence indicator in the electronic word of mouth variable, which obtained the highest score, confirms that user reviews play a dominant role in shaping consumer perceptions. Within the S-O-R framework, this illustrates that the stimulus in the form of social media content is processed at the organism stage through cognitive and affective interactions, which are then reflected in behaviors such as sharing information or providing recommendations (Febrianti & Ahmadi, 2024). This finding reinforces the argument that social media marketing not only directly affects consumers but also generates a chain effect through

electronic word of mouth, thereby extending its impact (Gasawneh et al., 2023; Iksyanti & Hidayat, 2022).

In addition, electronic word of mouth is proven to have a positive and significant effect on purchase intention and serves as a partial mediating variable in the relationship between social media marketing and purchase intention. This finding confirms that the formation of purchase intention is influenced not only by direct stimuli from companies but also by social validation through the experiences and recommendations of other consumers. In the context of the Stimulus-Organism-Response model, electronic word of mouth functions as the organism mechanism that bridges the stimulus and response, thereby strengthening confidence and positive perceptions prior to the purchasing decision (Liang et al., 2025; Mehrabian & Russell, 1974). Thus, these findings highlight the importance of integrating social media marketing strategies with the management of electronic word of mouth to build a more comprehensive influence on purchase intention (Sunaryanto & Oktaviandri, 2024; Kartini & Widagda, 2025).

CONCLUSION

This study aims to analyze the role of electronic word of mouth in mediating the effect of social media marketing on purchase intention among prospective Skintific consumers in Denpasar City. Based on the results of data analysis and discussion presented in the previous section, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. Social media marketing has a positive and significant effect on purchase intention. This indicates that the better the implementation of social media marketing, the higher the purchase intention of prospective consumers toward Skintific products.
2. Social media marketing has a positive and significant effect on electronic word of mouth. This shows that more effective social media marketing leads to more positive electronic word of mouth regarding Skintific products.
3. Electronic word of mouth has a positive and significant effect on purchase intention. This indicates that more positive electronic word of mouth leads to higher purchase intention among prospective consumers.
4. Electronic word of mouth acts as a partial mediating variable in the relationship between social media marketing and purchase intention. This suggests that social media marketing is able to increase purchase intention among prospective Skintific consumers through electronic word of mouth.

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